

Status of Scheduled Caste Women Entrepreneurs in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

Scheduled castes facing employment discrimination operates through traditional mechanisms, social hierarchy and culture. Less participation in employment not arise the issue of equal payment to male and female. Oppressed and politically marginalised group Dalits or Scheduled Castes have the periodical service of untouchable works like digging village graves, disposing dead animals, street cleaning and promoting to leather work, cobblers, agricultural work and manual scavengers etc. there is no wage no income in service. Intrinsically, wanting social development is high, getting education, employment, income, health, wealth etc. need to demanding. With the help of government and reservation system, entrepreneurship definitely improves the confidence level to live like others by adding social network. Through SC women entrepreneurship assist their community development beyond women empowerment.

1. Introduction

Gandhi was the first and foremost person who can realise the importance of the oppressed people's welfare and gave the poor of untouchable as a graceful term 'Harijan' (the people of God). Ambedkar was the strongest voice raised against the upper caste exploitation and depressing to oppressed people (Paswan and Jaideva, 2002)¹. He termed all the oppressed as 'Dalit' and fought for them with unflagging spirit even for getting Communal Award from the most instrumental to get the reservation clauses accepted the draft of the constitution. This quotas or reservation in state funded educational institutions and government sector jobs are the fundamental policy for the development of Scheduled Caste and other marginalised people. But growing privatisation of India's economy negatively affected the reservation since long years, up words of, other people are against the reservation for getting more chances to educate and employment, in encapsulation, the reality of Scheduled Caste's welfare is an apprehensive.

Scheduled castes facing employment discrimination (Jodhka2010)² operates through traditional mechanisms, social hierarchy and culture. Less participation in employment not arise the issue of equal payment to male and female. Oppressed and politically marginalised group Dalits or Scheduled Castes have the periodical service of untouchable works like digging village graves, disposing dead animals, street cleaning and promoting to leather work, cobblers, agricultural work and manual scavengers etc. there is no wage no income in service. Intrinsically, wanting social development is high, getting education, employment, income, health, wealth etc. need to demanding. With the help of government and reservation system, entrepreneurship definitely improves the confidence level to live like others by adding social network.

2. SC entrepreneurs

Jobs available under reservation system need to antagonize on growing privatisation in the state sector. Sprout of Dalit Entrepreneurs is not an exquisite; upwards of it is an existence in the case of Scheduled Caste. Self-employment in Scheduled Caste, marginalised group and socially excluded

community is the on-going discussion in the several studies. In the means of Scheduled Caste emancipation Dalit Indian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (DICC) which is inaugurated in 2005 April 14 on the behalf of Dr. BR Ambedkar's birth anniversary rejects the job reservation (Deshpande and Sharma 2013)³ by thinking positive. Increasing number of SC entrepreneurship is a signal of economic growth of the respective; this context reviews highly recommending entrepreneurship is an instrument for economic development of marginalised groups. In our rapid national growth, the serving of SC in firm ownership and employment generation over a period shows in sixth economic census is significantly Exemplary Elevation.

Chart 1 about hear

As per 2011 census of India 20.1 Crore people are living called Scheduled Caste, 15.1 Cr. are rural and 4.7 in urban.

Chart 2 about hear

Kerala is leading state of India in educationally and economically, 9.41 per cent Keralites are SC. In rural they are 54.2 per cent and in urban they are 36.5. Female SC shows the high share of percentage as 51.3 than male. Total literacy rate (Table1 in Appendix) of SC is 66.1 and female SC literacy is 56.5 in India. In Kerala SC female literacy is 85.1 percentage total. According to Economic Census 2013, total share of employment for SC in India 11.7 per cent (table 2 in Appendix) and establishment or enterprise ownership is 12.2 per cent. In India starting a generation of role models for SC people to who are interested to do a business (Kapur et al, 2014)⁴, a life of experience book to for all SC entrepreneurs.

3. Women in Scheduled Caste

Above 50 of female significantly engaging in economic activities, perhaps; female dominant Kerala helps to increase the participation in education not in other variables. While, women are strikingly homogenous across social groups (Field et al, 2010)⁵. Least restricted people SC almost have the highest odds ratio in participating in agriculture wage employment (SrivastavaN & R, 2010)⁶ and also women are following this

undoubtedly. Rare learning of SC women studies shows the disparity with other people.

Shorage of uneducated parents and less amalgamated society may be the real struggling factors of SC women to entering in to economic environment. Social network should be ascending by the influence of kudumbasree and Self Help Groups in Kerala (Raghavan,⁷). It is helps to increase personal traits as well as group and social activities.

4. SC women entrepreneurs

Recently, scant of SC women entrepreneurs defying by SC like Manju Rani (Kapur et al, 2014) is one out of twenty because the high problems facing by women than men (economic, political, financial, social etc.) ie, push and pull factors (Goyal and Parkash, 2011)⁸ affects their confidence level. Problems of women entrepreneurs in India (Kumbhar V, 2013)⁹ a) Absence of Definite Agenda of Life b) Absence of Balance between Family and Career Obligations c) Poor Degree of Financial Freedom d) No Direct Ownership of the Property e) Paradox of Entrepreneurial Skill & Finance f) No Awareness about Capacities g) Low Ability to Bear Risk h) Problems of Work with Male Workers i) Negligence by Financial Institutions j) Lack of Self-Confidence k) Lack of Professional Education l) Mobility Constraints m) Lack of Interaction with Successful Entrepreneurs. Necessitates of Women Entrepreneurship to remove social, economic and educational constrains not solved after more than half-a-century has passed since independency of India (Tiwari S and Tiwary A, 2007)¹⁰.

Out of 9 per cent SC try to participate their contribution in Employment in Kerala 4.0 per cent and establishment is 4.9 per cent. 2013 economic census says the 12.1 per cent of SC women Female share of enterprise ownership and in Kerala there is 6.78 per cent to comparing other categories (Table 3 in Appendix).

Table:1 Percentage of SC women Enterprises and Employment share from total Women Entrepreneurs in Kerala

Districs	SCE	
	Share of Establishment %	Share of Employment %
Kasargod	6.06	5.88
Kannur	2.78	2.69
Wayanad	3.98	3.98
Kozikkod	4.68	4.58
Malappuram	6.65	6.29
Palakkad	13.82	12.76
Thrissur	8.59	7.81
Eranakulam	5.89	5.34
Idukki	8.13	7.45
Kottayam	5.62	4.97
Alappuza	6.36	5.85
Pathanamthitta	9.46	8.58

Kollam	6.88	6.39
Trivandram	7.01	6.66

Source: Computing from Report on sixth Economic Census 2013, Gender Statistics 2017, Department of Economics & Statistics Government of Kerala

District Palakkad, Pathanamthitta, Thrissur have the highest rank of SC establishments and in share of employment Kerala. Population variance is positively affecting the number of women in the entrepreneurship (Iyer et al, 2011)¹¹. With-out Wayanad District, remains are 50 per cent and above female SC population than SC male (see table 5 in Appendix).

If the consideration of population for the participations in establishment and employment must referring the entrepreneurial enabling ages and checking the significance level of different age groups toward the performance of SC women.

Table 2 Correlation different ages toward Establishment and Employment sharing of SC women

Age groups	establishment	Sig.	employment	Sig.
20-24	.781**	.001	.782**	.001
24-29	.766**	.001	.771**	.001
30-34	.786**	.001	.795**	.001
35-39	.786**	.001	.795**	.001
40-44	.780**	.001	.791**	.001
45-49	.813**	.000	.825**	.000
50-54	.814**	.000	.828**	.000
55-59	.807**	.000	.824**	.000
60-64	.788**	.001	.797**	.001
65-69	.779**	.001	.790**	.001

**P<.05

Age group 45-49, 50-54, 55-59 are highly correlated in to the level of establishment and employment of SC women in Kerala.

5. Conclusion

Kapur et al and jodhka SS says this is the first generation of SC entrepreneurs in India; some role models are generated with the help of DICCI and the positive change of social environment. History shows the women empowerment is a slowly process, the importance of entrepreneurship in women empowerment is significantly working among women. Other points are Self Helps Groups in Villages and role of Kudumbasree in rural areas are awfully accommodating the oppressed women especially SC women. Through SC women entrepreneurship assist their community development beyond women empowerment. It is true time to study the level of interaction on Entrepreneurship of SC women for showing their social and economic development. In future, hopefully, suggesting the number of significant age groups of SC women may increase, 30 plus ages have to companions of entrepreneurship especially for community development by sound of networking with other caste with women empowerment.

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Appendix

Chart 1: Population Share of SC in India in Crore

Source: Population Census 2011

Chart 2: Population Share of SC in Kerala

Source: Population Census 2011, Gender statistics, Department of Economics & Statistics Government of Kerala 2017 & Hand Book on Social Welfare Statistics, Government of India Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment Department of Social Justice & Empowerment Statistics Division New Delhi, January 2016

Table 1; Literacy Rate

	India				Kerala			
	Total	Female	SC	SC-Female	Total	Female	SC	SC-Female
Literacy Rate 2011	73.4	64.4	66.1	56.5	94.4	92.1	88.7	85.1

Source: Hand book on Social Welfare Statistics, Government of India Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment Department of Social Justice & Empowerment Statistics Division New Delhi, January 2016

Table 2; Share of Enterprises and Employment of SC

	India		Kerala	
	Total	SC	Total	SC
Share of Enterprise Ownership 2013	89.39%	12.2%	88.7%	4.9%
Share of employment 2013	78.52%	11.7%	26.48%	4.0%

Source: Economic Census of India 2013, Report on sixth Economic Census of Kerala 2013

Table 3; Share of SC women Enterprises ownership

	India					Kerala				
	Total	SC	ST	OBC	Others	Total	SC	ST	OBC	Others
Female Share of Enterprise Ownership 2013	13.76	12.1	6.9	40.6	40.2	27.24	6.78	1.72	59.61	31.89

Source: Economic Census of India 2013, Report on sixth Economic Census of Kerala 2013

Table 4; Share of Establishment and Employment under women entrepreneurs in Kerala

Districts	Rural		Urban		Total	
	<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>	<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>	<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>
Kasargod	43412	46341	20274	22555	63686	68896
Kannur	34730	40270	32081	40762	66871	81032
Wayanad	16512	22570	415	654	16927	23224
Kozikkod	21017	25327	36689	46477	57706	71804
Malappuram	42088	49020	29122	34393	71210	83413
Palakkad	40634	50358	10391	14561	51025	64919
Thrissur	22034	26297	42009	53866	64043	80163
Eranakulam	37958	47980	53616	75969	91573	123949
Idukki	30689	39308	1084	1719	31773	41027
Kottayam	47975	58761	12529	19294	60504	78055
Alappuza	30653	37904	34505	45388	65158	83292
Pathanamthitta	34634	42217	3287	4929	37921	47146
Kollam	46290	58648	21276	30954	67586	89602
Thiruvananthapuram	85516	107577	82438	102926	167954	210503

Source: Report on sixth Economic Census, Department of Economics & Statistics Government of Kerala 2013

Table 5; Share of Establishment and Employment under SC women entrepreneurs in Kerala

Districts	SC Female Population	Rural		Urban		Total	
		<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>	<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>	<i>establishment</i>	<i>Employment</i>
Kasargod	26898 (50.48)	2983	3113	877	940	3860	4053
Kannur	43090 (51.70)	100	1122	860	1058	1860	2180
Wayanad	16172 (49.64)	558	905	17	20	675	925
Kozikkod	101912 (51.16)	1005	1304	1700	1989	2705	3293
Malappuram	156709 (50.84)	3007	3353	1735	1898	4742	5251
Palakkad	206382 (51.11)	5826	6863	1228	1422	7054	8285
Thrissur	167870 (51.76)	1994	2229	3511	4032	5505	6261

Eranakulam	136838 (50.98)	2270	2671	3132	3959	5402	6630
Idukki	73087 (50.24)	2582	3036	16	22	2598	3058
Kottayam	78406 (50.94)	2970	3335	436	548	3406	3883
Alappuza	104028 (51.70)	2284	2657	1861	2219	4145	4876
Pathanamthitta	85523 (52.00)	3427	3838	162	209	3589	4047
Kollam	170462 (51.93)	3677	4343	975	1390	4652	5733
Trivandram	194388 (52.12)	5697	6997	6091	7035	11788	14035

Source: Report on sixth Economic Census 2013, Gender Statistics 2017, Department of Economics & Statistics Government of Kerala

SC Female population in different age group -2011 Census

Districts	20-24	25-29	30-34	35-39	40-44	45-49	50-54	55-59	60-64	65-69
Kasargod	2722	2978	2293	2345	1831	1734	1213	1019	840	687
Kannur	3430	3974	3825	3768	3344	3191	2534	2305	1842	1309
Wayanad	1281	1373	1354	1490	1172	1182	846	749	568	428
Kozikkod	7469	8923	8628	9535	8376	7628	5768	5388	4269	3127
Malappuram	15045	15440	12769	13218	10952	9995	7057	6091	5723	4077
Palakkad	19376	19887	15741	17758	13505	13852	9547	9246	8609	6548
Thrissur	12738	14428	13436	15991	14052	13033	9613	8531	7322	5650
Eranakulam	9554	11159	11008	12614	12019	11427	8532	7386	5704	4551
Idukki	6372	6753	5815	6680	5466	5477	4601	3554	2165	1772
Kottayam	5366	6418	6523	7017	6332	5973	4763	4147	3281	2585
Alappuza	7192	8857	8895	9665	8333	8076	6138	5638	4594	3498
Pathanamthitta	6202	7687	7102	7899	6580	6717	5042	4544	3512	2779
Kollam	13340	15988	14235	15862	12665	12386	8923	9160	6635	5277
Trivandram	16268	16956	15632	17057	14644	14951	11162	10379	7847	5849

Source: Gender Statistics 2017, Department of Economics & Statistics Government of Kerala.